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DESIGN OF INTERACTIVE INDOOR WAYFINDING MAP FOR ELDERLY USERS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to establish an appropriate design of interactive indoor wayfinding maps for elderly users. The user interface of interactive wayfinding maps, including visual representation and operational interface, should satisfy the needs of elderly users. Map use by elderly participants was explored using methods of observation and interview. Protocol analysis was used to understand user needs and experiences. This paper suggested design guidelines of visual representation from the results of analysis. Based on literature review and user experience, this paper proposes a conceptual framework of user interface using a non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom that integrates the operations of re-center zoom and hierarchy-structured zoom.

Keywords: Wayfinding map, interaction design, aging.

INTRODUCTION

Wayfinding maps assist people in orienting themselves and navigating between locations in physical space. Passini (1984) noted that wayfinding maps have two key functions: to provide information leading to the identification of a route; and to provide information leading toward spatial comprehension of a particular place. As information technology continues to advance rapidly, maps are digitalized to be more dynamic and interactive. However, indoor wayfinding maps, such as “you-are-here” maps in public places, rarely designed to include interactive technology. Aging lowers physiological abilities related to vision, speech, hearing, and psychomotor skills; and also

diminishes psychological abilities related to attention, memory, and learning (Hawthorn, 1998). When elderly people use information tools, problems of user intention and acceptance, beyond personal ability, may emerge. Using appropriately designed maps, elderly people can manage rapidly changing physical spaces, toward easier and more independent lives.

For most indoor environments, signs and maps are highly common elements of wayfinding systems. Butler, Acquino, Hissong, and Scott (1993) noted that signs are more efficient than maps for wayfinding tasks, suggesting that studying maps require more time than do signs. Studying a map and memorizing a path are cognitive loads. A sign benefits for providing locations’ names and directions simultaneously. However, Butler et al. (1993) suggested that a sign system may be complex and impractical if there are a large number of goals. A support system can be helpful to shorten the functionality and usability gap between signs and maps.

This research developed a conceptual framework for user interface in wayfinding maps. The user interfaces and displays are shown and operated on fixed devices such as wayfinding maps or public kiosks. To reduce the cognitive loads experienced by elderly users, the conceptual framework provides a simplified interface with a non-predefined hierarchy-structured map.

DESIGN ISSUES OF WAYFINDING MAPS

Wayfinding is a behavior that involves locating the proper path toward physical destinations in our daily lives. Golledge (1999) stated that, “wayfinding is the process of determining and following a path or route between an origin and a destination. It is a purposive, directed, and motivated activity.” To find an

appropriate route, a person must be able to identify origins and destinations, to determine turn angles, to identify lengths and directions of movement, to recognize en route and distant landmarks. A person must have a strategy for integrating all spatial information into a frame of reference and for selecting paths within that frame.

Considering the form and presentation of wayfinding information, Lloyd (1993) found that the interpretability of a map depends upon how well visual features of the map carry information about the area the map describes. Interpretability and detail of information can conflict (Hunt & Waller, 1999). For example, distance information is much more clearly represented in plans than are perspective views. However perceiving the perspective views may be easier using previous visual experience of the scenery being depicted.

Wayfinding maps involve numerous properties. View is an essential attribute when simulating 3-D vision in maps. There are several types of views: (a) axonometric view: retaining a true-to-scale plan and a view without a vanishing point so that parallel lines are represented as parallel; (b) perspective view: a view from a specified point; and c) mixed view: combination of views; for example, plans used to show land and realistic pictures used to show landmarks (Passini, 1984).

Lynch (1960) stated that landmarks a basic element of a city's image. Landmarks can be recognized from long distances for their distinct visual forms or prominent positions. Representing landmarks in wayfinding maps can be an effective attribute for improving the user experience. Burnett (2000) proposed the use of landmarks in vehicle navigation systems, believing that: (a) landmarks are a core component of peoples' mental representations of large-scale space; (b) landmarks have been evaluated by drivers as the second most popular type of information (after left-right directions); and (c) landmarks can improve the usability of vehicle navigation systems in effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction.

Map orientation also affects the efficiency and process of user perception and cognition. There are several methods for arranging map orientation: (a) track-up: directions displayed en route as viewers travel; (b) north-up: the traditional method

providing a fixed directional reference, which most people are used to and with which further transformation is unnecessary; and (c) modified north-up: based on north-up maps, adding symbols indicating a user's position and view direction (Ware, 2000). Levine, Marchon, and Hanley (1984) suggested that YAH maps should be aligned with the terrain; this is similar to the track-up concept. Warren and Scott (1993) found that users prefer to align maps with the environment. They also confirmed that wayfinding task performance is higher when the involved map is aligned, as opposed to when it is not aligned with the environment. In addition, Warren (1994) discovered that users preferred to use the oblique map (displaying an axonometric view) in an upright-but-misaligned orientation rather than in a non-upright-but-aligned orientation. However, user performance was lower when using upright-but-misaligned oblique maps.

OPERATIONAL INTERFACE OF INTERACTIVE WAYFINDING MAPS

Hawthorn (2000) proposed interface design suggestions for elderly users in several dimensions. In HCI research viewing a large image that does not fit a smaller screen is a well-known problem. Various approaches have been proposed to support browsing large maps on screens (Plaisant, Carr, & Shneiderman, 1995). In theory, scrolling or panning can browse every part of a large image. With zooming, it is possible to provide an overview of images using various scales. As Harrower and Sheesley (2005) indicated, few studies have sought to understand how panning and zooming should be designed when improving the usability of web maps. The conclusion is that no single pan or zoom method is both highly capable and highly efficient. A pan/zoom design is more effective only when it is appropriate for particular users and tasks. When considering map interface for efficiency of use, Fitts's law can be used as a basic guideline for designing an interface to contend with time and distance factors (Fitts, 1954). Fitts's law models the relationships among movement, time, distance, and accuracy for people engaged in rapidly aimed movements (Soukoreff & MacKenzie, 2004). Fitts's law is a model of human movement, predicting the time required to move rapidly from a starting

position to a final target area as a function of the distance to the target and the size of the target. It can be applied in both the physical and virtual worlds. According to Fitts's law, movement is faster when a short distance is needed to manipulate the mouse to complete the operations of a function. Therefore, in theory, all controls should be placed near each other for efficiency. In an interactive map, for example, all pan buttons for different directions should be placed together for quick pan operations. Similarly, zooming with an original map center can be used repeatedly and quickly, because moving the mouse is not necessary.

When considering map interface for learnability, arranging controls according to the directions of the corresponding functions is natural. Norman (1988) explained the principle of natural mapping, which addresses the relationship between two objects or concepts, such as a control in user interface and its response. If the mapping appears natural (that is, visible), is closely related to the desired outcome, and provides immediate feedback, learning and remembering relevant information is easier. Following the principle of natural mapping, a designer may use a spatial analogy. For example, to move an object up, the user moves the control up; and to control an array of objects, controls are arranged in the same pattern as the objects. The design of an interactive map interface is a trade-off between efficiency and learnability. In the zoom/pan example, Fitts's law provides a fundamental understanding about the efficiency of the layout and use of web map interfaces. Norman's principle of natural mapping and mental model is an effective guideline for designing interfaces that are easier to learn and remember. However, using larger and more closely placed buttons cannot always match natural mapping. In many applications, the principles conflict with one another. The designers must then find an appropriate solution for resolving the conflict.

EXPLORATION OF MAP USER EXPERIENCE

Field exploration was conducted to investigate elderly users' experience using wayfinding map at real sites. Tasks were assigned to explore unfamiliar places using wayfinding maps. Methods involving

thinking aloud, observation, and interview were used to collect data.

PARTICIPANTS

A study on the policy of aging in labor by the Employment, Labour, and Social Affairs Committee of the OECD defined the elderly as people above the age of 55 (Auer, 2002). The participants were recruited from elderly volunteers of an art museum. Six elderly participants, two male and four female, were recruited for this stage.

MATERIAL AND TEST SITE

Two maps of the test sites with different views were made for comparison: the first is a plan view and the second is a perspective view (see Figures 1 and 2). The first and second floors of three buildings on the authors' campus were used as the test sites.

Figure 1. Wayfinding map: plan view (Buildings A and B).

Figure 2. Wayfinding map: perspective view (Buildings A and B).

TASKS

The test for each participant required approximately one hour. Tasks were assigned one at a time for the participant to find the ways to specific rooms in the

buildings. They could use both maps when necessary. The maps were printed in A3 size. The investigator employed the “think aloud” method using audio recordings to collect verbal protocol from the participants. While finding the ways, the participant was asked to talk aloud about his/her behaviors and thinking. After all the tasks were completed, a half-structured interview was conducted. The investigator asked each participant questions about the experience using maps in route planning, decision-making, and decision-execution sessions. Finally, the participant was asked to draw a sketch map of the site and routes.

Figure 3. Sketch map by Participant C.

RESULTS

All protocol data were coded and classified. All participants could complete all tasks without significant difficulty. While making their wayfinding plan, most participants selected the shortest routes on the main roads. Some participants used landmarks as reference information to match their expected image with the correct direction. Most participants favored checking the maps when encountering unfamiliar environments. The results were interpreted according to the following dimensions.

Individual difference

- Gender: Female participants showed anxiety in wayfinding.
- Social experience: Elderly participants tended to ask help from others. The behavior of others can be a clue toward showing the appropriate route.
- Cognitive ability: The ability to collect and understand spatial information is affected by

aging. Spatial ability declines with weaker short-term memory.

Spatial information

- Too much information resulted in the wayfinding difficulties for participants.
- Landmarks could serve as references in participants' wayfinding processes. Prominent landmarks could lead users to smaller landmarks or target locations.
- The perspective map helped participants match between maps and the real world. Most participants believed that the perspective map was more appropriate for understanding spatial structure.
- Spatial relationships among floors are difficult to determine. The perspective map might help participants in the problem with its realistic image.

Architecture design

- Spatial cognition could be altered after passing the connecting path between buildings. The original sense of direction could be lost.
- In buildings, the indoor spatial structure might be too complicated for participants to construct an inner cognitive map.

USER EVALUATION OF MODIFIED VISUAL REPRESENTATION

A questionnaire was used to conduct user evaluations of the proposed visual representation of the wayfinding maps using different views. There were eight questions for each map. A Likert scale with five levels was used to determine the levels of agreement to the questions.

PARTICIPANTS AND MATERIAL

The participants were recruited from elderly volunteers of two museums. Twenty-five elderly participants, 8 male and 17 female, were recruited for this stage. The two maps of the previous test site with different views were modified according to the design concept (see Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4. Modified wayfinding map: plan view (Buildings A and B).

Figure 5. Modified wayfinding map: perspective view (Buildings A, B, and C).

QUESTIONNAIRE

Part 1: Demographic data and map use experience

This part consists of questions regarding demographic data, such as age, sex, and education, as well as questions regarding map use and wayfinding experience, such as frequency and familiarity of map use.

Part 2: Subjective evaluation of map use (one copy for each map)

This part consists of questions regarding learnability, legibility, and subjective satisfaction:

1. The colors in the map can help me interpret the map information.
2. It is easy to read the map clearly.
3. I can understand the spatial layout of the map.
4. I can determine how far it is to the target location by the map.
5. I can match the map to the real world easily.
6. Regarding its design, the map is easy to use.
7. The size of the graphics and text are appropriate.
8. The map can help me understand the relationships among the floors.

RESULTS:

In the subjective evaluation, a repeated measure ANOVA was used to compare the mean agreement between the two views. The results show that there are significant differences in Q3, Q4, Q5, and Q8 (see Table 1). The perspective view is superior to the plan view in the four questions.

It is possible that the perspective can help elderly users understand the spatial layout and know how far it is to the target location. Elderly users may be able to match the map to the real world easily. Most significantly, the perspective map can help elderly users understand the spatial relationships among the floors. There is no significant difference in legibility and subjective satisfaction. In general, the perspective map is preferred because it is easier for elderly users to understand the mapping between maps and the world using similar perceived images.

Question	Mean	F	p-value
Q1	Plan: 3.84 Persp.: 4.04	1.340	0.259
Q2	Plan: 3.84 Persp.: 3.96	0.269	0.609
Q3	Plan: 3.60 Persp.: 4.04	6.453	0.018*
Q4	Plan: 3.56 Persp.: 4.00	6.739	0.016*
Q5	Plan: 3.72 Persp.: 4.12	7.885	0.010*
Q6	Plan: 3.72 Persp.: 4.04	4.179	0.053
Q7	Plan: 3.72 Persp.: 4.04	2.707	0.114
Q8	Plan: 3.58 Persp.: 4.29	13.146	0.001**

Table 1. Repeated measure ANOVA between two views. Note: * p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01.

A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF HIERARCHY-STRUCTURED MAP AS OPERATIONAL INTERFACE

A conceptual framework for user interface of interactive wayfinding maps is discussed in this section. The concept of the framework is similar to those of predefined hierarchy-structured maps. For some predefined districts, hierarchy-structured maps can be used for quick browsing through the large area (see Figure 6). The user can select an item

among others using the same level in the hierarchy. The result is a close view of selected item, which involves zooming in the map using one-click selection. If all districts are predefined and users are familiar with the hierarchy, a hierarchy-structured map can be an efficient navigation tool. In this research, it is called as a predefined hierarchy-structured map. In general, navigating such a map using any type of zoom function can be understood as navigation in a hierarchy. A hierarchy is similar to a tree, not a network. A user simply selects one item to travel inside a district. The user can then travel further in the hierarchy or return to the original map area.

Figure 6. Predefined hierarchy-structured map: (a) Japan; (b) Kanto region of Japan.

The re-center zoom is similar to the predefined hierarchy-structured zoom in the operation involving a single click/touch to zoom in. This research proposes a conceptual framework of a user interface using a non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom that integrates the operation of re-center zoom and hierarchy-structured zoom (see Figure 7). In the user interface, re-center zoom is set as default function without using the previous function selection. The zoom-out function can also be replaced by a “back”

button, ensuring that users can return to the original area on the maps. Users can navigate in the map using a manner similar to the predefined hierarchy-structured zoom. However, any type of map can be used in the framework without major modification. Because the re-center zoom couples zoom-in with a pan function, the pan buttons can be eliminated. With no horizontal links in the navigation diagram, the interface is much simpler to use in operational and visual representation.

In general, when using the non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom, any map can be applied to navigate in a hierarchy, even if the hierarchy is not predefined. According to the concept of navigation in a hierarchy, maps are not necessary to be spatially continuous or precise. The top-down structure can connect places with some conceptual neighbors. The representation of nodes in a hierarchy or tree can be any type of image, not only a map-like image.

Figure 7. Navigation diagram of the proposed conceptual framework with non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom design.

DISCUSSION

This research proposes a conceptual framework of a simple, non-predefined hierarchy-structured (re-center) zoom design that can be more efficient and easy to learn than a camera-like (original center) pan-and-zoom design. We can compare the usability and satisfaction of prototypes using different views. It is possible that the usability and satisfaction of a non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom design is more efficient than a camera-like pan-and-zoom design using a specific view. The performance of non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom can depend on other factors. In addition, the traditional pan-and-zoom function is adequate for maps with the plan view, but may not be compatible in concept with maps having the perspective view. In a traditional pan-and-zoom design, it is natural to place the pan buttons on the spatially-related

positions corresponding to the directions of the pan functions. However, users do not always know the exact meaning of the functions that the designer assigned. When a pan button is clicked, the question remains whether the user should move the frame (or the window) around the map or move the actual map itself. Although some may argue that this could be learned easily by trial-and-error, according to Norman (1988), different mental models are formed during such a process, potentially misleading users into thinking that they are moving the map itself, even though the designer had intended the users to move the frame.

In the non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom design that this research proposes, only a direct click/touch is required to zoom in. The center of the map also changes with the same step. No further panning is necessary. The simple layout and use of operational interface can eliminate the possibility of obtaining incorrect mental models. Furthermore, it is possible that re-center zoom includes a re-center pan function, emphasizing how to feel and be familiar with the relationship between operations and panning direction.

CONCLUSION

This research conducted field exploration to understand map user experience. Design guidelines of visual representation are suggested in this paper. Differences between plan and perspective views were compared using quantitative method. This research proposes a conceptual framework to improve the usability and satisfaction of user interface. The discussions suggest that traditional original-center zoom can be a more effective operational interface for providing quicker and more efficient searches. However, non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom can provide an intuitive way to zoom-in. Future investigations and evaluations are necessary to improve the proposed user interface of interactive wayfinding maps. It is important to evaluate the proper size and position of interactive objects in interface for elderly users. In addition, creating clear conceptual models of new environments could be a more powerful solution for future interface design. The problem for elderly users in the future, as well as now, is not only decline of abilities, but also a lack of previous

experience and conceptual models. The transparency of conceptual models could help elderly users' learning beyond ability limitation.

Some evaluations are required to test the hypotheses that a non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom design can be more efficient than a camera-like pan-and-zoom design; and that a non-predefined hierarchy-structured zoom design can be preferred to a camera-like pan-and-zoom design in satisfaction. Suggestions for further study are as follows:

1. Prototypes integrating visual presentation and operational interface could be developed using systematic variations in views, landmarks, colors, and other cartographic elements.
2. The usability and satisfaction of prototypes using different views could be tested to understand the correlation between view and operational interface.

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